

Prevalence and Determinants of Psychoactive Substances Use among Youths in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the prevalence and determinants of psychoactive substances use among youths in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State. To achieve the aim of this study, four (4) research questions were raised as guide. The design adopted for this study was a descriptive cross-sectional survey while multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select a total of 189 youths from the respective communities in the study area for the study. The instrument for data collection was semi-structured questionnaire constructed in consonance with the study objectives. The questionnaire was duly validated with high reliability coefficient. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics including frequency counts, simple percentages, weighted mean score, and Chi-square statistic. Data analysis was conducted with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Results of the study revealed that a majority 164 (86.7%) of the students have used psychoactive substances and same proportion are currently using these substances. The most used psychoactive substances are alcohol 160 (97.6%). The significant reasons why these students involve in the used of these substances were; to conform to peers (3.51±0.36), boost confidence (3.74±0.32), and for experimentation (3.12±0.17). The demographic characteristics of youths associated with the use of psychoactive substances include sex, age, place of residence, and family type ($p < 0.05$). Based on these findings, it was recommended that an enlightenment programme should be designed and implemented in communities especially in Calabar Metropolis to create awareness on the health and legal implications of using psychoactive substances.

Keywords: Prevalence, Determinants, Psycho-active, Substance and Youths.

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Background of the Study

Substances are available agents and drugs used for psychoactive purpose. Being psychoactive are their ability to spur the mind or mental process unto desirable or aversive actions which may be at variance with societal expectation. They are harmful or hazardous to the body when taken in high dosage and in people with low tolerance. Substance or drug abuse is consumption of drug in a quantity or methods harmful to the person or society (Ksir & Charles, 2022).

According to World Health Organization (WHO) 2021, Alcohol and Cannabis remains the most widely used psychoactive substance in African Region. World Drug Report (2012) stated that alcohol, amphetamines, barbiturates, cannabis, benzodiazepines, cocaine, hallucinogens, methaqualone, and opioids are major substance of abuse. The highest prevalence and increase in use are being reported in West and Central Africa with rates between 5.2% and 13.5%. This is followed by Amphetamine and Methamphetamine as the second widely abused substance. Others are benzodiazepines (Diazepam), chlorpromazine, inhalants and injectables widely used by children and youths in Sierra Leone and other West African countries. According to Gobir, Sambo, Bashir, Olorukoba, Ezeh, Bello, Usman, Salaudeen, Joseph, Bashar & Omole, (2017), drug abuse is prevalent in almost all localities in Africa including Nigeria, and the most accessible are Tramadol and Marijuana which are used to enhance farming and laborious activities.

The actual cause of substance abuse is not known, but these two predominant theories: genetic predisposition and learned habit from others is linked into the caused (World Drug Report, 2022). Global report also reveals that evolution of the complex illicit drug problem is clearly driven by a range of factors. These factors include Socio-demographic trends such as population, gender, age and the rate of urbanization (Walitzer & Dearing, 2016). In America, nationwide survey on use of substance abuse showed 48.2% consumed illicit agent at any point in life, 41.2% took alcohol and 19.2% smoked tobacco cigarettes (Johnston, O'Malley, Bachman & Schulenberg, 2021).

One of the key impacts of illicit drug use on society is the negative health consequences experienced by its members. Substance abuse causes heavy financial burden on individuals, families, and society. It was reported that harmful use of alcohol results in 3.3 million deaths per year. On average every person in the world within the age of 15 years or older drinks 6.2 liters of pure alcohol every year. From above, less than half of the population (38.3%) drinks alcohol, meaning that those who do drink consume on average 17 liters of pure alcohol annually. At least 15.3 million persons have drug use disorders. Injecting drug use reported in 148 countries, of which 120 report HIV infection among this population (McHugh, Votaw, Sugarman & Greenfield, 2018).

In adolescence, experimentation with drugs is quite common among youths in Nigeria because at this age, the young people want to explore due to curiosity, influence from peers and for stress relieve. The use of gateway drugs like alcohol, tobacco and tramadol from an early age increases the risk of using other hard drugs later. Some adolescents may experiment

the drugs and stop (or continue to use them occasionally) without having negative complications while others develop an addiction that makes them susceptible to other dangerous drugs that cause significant harm to themselves and possibly family/community members (National Institute on Drug Abuse, 2023).

National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA) (2013) observed that risk of youths becoming drug abuser is related to parents' protection and association with other users. More so, impacts of specific risk and protective factors depend on the youth's age. In that, the family only gains control while the child is young, but when he joins higher school, the drug abusing peers becomes more significant risk factor (Ialongo, Werthamer, Kellam, Brown, Wang, & Lin, 2019). In some families where there is early detection and intervention to control risk factors, in form of guiding against aggressive behaviors and avoiding poor self-control, it helps change the child's life pathway towards positive behaviors (Catalano, Haggerty, Fleming, Brewer & Gainey, 2012). Though these measures are believed to be protective it is not effective for all group of youths due to age, gender, ethnicity, environmental background, and culture (Catalano, Haggerty, Fleming, Brewer & Gainey (2022).

Influence of substance consumption and abuse has caused lots of school dropout, failures, vices, lawlessness, street children and increased violence. It is on these backgrounds that the researcher is poised to conduct this study to examine prevalence and influence of psychoactive substance abuse among youths in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State.

Statement of problem

Psychoactive Substance use is not a strange phenomenon; the global, regional, and national dimension of it had gained global documentation. It is in recognition of the complexity of the problem that 26th June of every year has been declared as the International Day Against Abuse and illicit trafficking by United Nations. As the 2018 National Drug Use Survey (NDUS) revealed, in Nigeria at that time there were around 14.3 million drug users of which close to 3 million suffered from a drug use disorder. The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) said recent statistics have revealed that 40 per cent of Nigerian youth between 18 and 35 years are deeply involved in the abuse of drugs.

The physical, psychological, social, and economic consequences of the drug problems among individual have been of concern as most victims have fallen to the cold hands of untimely death through motor accidents, crime, and incarceration. This phenomenon though cuts across all ages, is more common among young people who persistently abuse substances and as such experience an array of problems including academic difficulties, health related problems (including mental health) involvement in social vices such as stealing, bullying, rape, secret cult activities which may have negative consequences on family members, community and the entire society. Youth under the influence of this stimulant are often involve in crimes, juvenile delinquencies, hooliganism, rioting and mental breakdown. Psychoactive substance use leads to dependence syndrome - a cluster of behavioural, cognitive, and physiological phenomena that develop after repeated substance use and that typically include a strong desire to take the drug, difficulties in controlling its use, persisting

in its use despite harmful consequences, a higher priority given to drug use than to other activities and obligations, increased tolerance, and sometimes a physical withdrawal state. Observations have shown that the consequences of using some psychoactive drugs include cirrhosis of the liver, wrinkles, emphysema, and lung cancer.

Youth are the most active in the society and the look up on to them because they are the future leaders of tomorrow as well as the resources of any nation. In their active state, they are expected to be in school to acquire knowledge that will enable them cope with the future challenges, the school is also to inform and educate the student on certain attitude, lifestyle and behaviour that are beneficial for their health and that of the society (Startertion, 2019). The people particularly vulnerable to substance abuse include secondary school students, the abused or neglected youths, the homeless, the physically or mentally challenged, school dropouts, children of substance abusers, street children and the poor.

Ksir and Charles (2022) further asserted that one determinant of psychoactive drug use is family upbringing. This was seen in Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Calabar, where a male youth expose the father who brought him for admission of abnormal behaviour due to substance intoxication (cocaine). While the process was ongoing, the father gave history of his daily, weekly, and yearly drug consumption that resulted in dispossession of his valuable laptop, cabinets, and smart phone at giveaway price to a friend. In the same scene, the patient grudgingly vacates the history seat and usher the father to equally sit. He thereafter relayed to the nurse the father's consumption history and quarreled because the father is not presented for consequential admission (FNPH/NA/CN-OPE, 2021).

It is important to determine the prevalence and determinants of this emerging syndrome among youths who will become the future leaders. However, there is paucity of up-to-date literature on this subject in Calabar Metropolis, creating a gap in knowledge. This study is therefore undertaken to fill this gap by investigating the prevalence and determinants of psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State.

Aim of Study

The main aim of the study was to determine the prevalence and determinant of psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State.

Specific Objectives

The specific objective of the study includes:

1. Determine the prevalence of psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis
2. Identify the types of psychoactive substances commonly used among youths in Calabar Metropolis
3. Examine the reasons for psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis

4. Ascertain the demographic determinants of psychoactive substances use among youths in Calabar Metropolis.

Research questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the prevalence of psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis?
2. What are the types of psychoactive substance commonly use among youths in Calabar Metropolis?
3. What are the reasons for psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis?
4. What are the demographic determinants of psychoactive substances use among youths in Calabar Metropolis?

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study when dissemination would help in creating intervention by creating awareness and encouraging behavioural changes among the youths.

The findings which will reveal the reason and types of psychoactive substance would help the school administration and drug law enforcement agency to monitor the population at risk and strengthen policies. The findings would also assist the development of counseling and training programs to eliminate the menace among youths thus giving room for improved physical, social, emotional and spiritual wellbeing of the youths.

The findings would add to the existing body of knowledge on this topic and serve as a reference material to students and researchers respectively.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework adopted for this study was the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). This theory as used in psychology, education and communication holds that individual's knowledge acquisition is related to observing people within his immediate environment during interactions, experiences and outside media. The theory was modified by Albert Bandura in 1986 in his Social Learning Theory. It states that "when people observe a model performing a behavior and the consequences of that behavior, they remember the sequence of events of that behavior and uses the information to guide their subsequent behaviors". Thus, observing a model prompts behavior of the viewer to engage in a behavior they had already learnt (Bandura, 2008). This means that people do not learn new behaviors by trial and error, but that survival of humanity is reliance on replication of other people's action. Then depending on whether his predecessors were rewarded or punished for their behavior as outcome, the observer may choose to imitate their behavior.

Figure 1 Bandura's model of Social Cognitive Theory representing the triangular relationship between the three main factors of human behaviour (Bandura, 2001)

Application of the theory to the study

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) constitutes 3 basic components that interrelate inwardly and outwardly. They are Personal Determinants, Behavioral Determinants and Environmental Determinants.

Personal Determinants

This is also called cognitive determinants made up of moral development/thought contents, affective self-reaction and Commitment to social norms. They comprise of what an individual inherited from parents, developmental background and what he wishes for self. As people relates in society they seek after what is good for them to enhance their wellbeing.

Behavioral Determinants

This involves action that portrays academic integrity and professionalism. In this domain individual is curious seeking for what benefits academic and professional endowment to build his behaviors and lacks concern with entertainments or social pleasures. Individuals here are reading, practicing, learning, inquiring over unknown and writing down new ideas.

Environmental Determinants

At this domain people are interested pleasing the community and abiding with societal norms. They are afraid of being sanctioned, abide on codes of conduct, relate freely with classmates, peers and faculty friends, easily sociable and attract many lovers. Individual here tries to please friends and goes extra miles live to their expectation. It is on this domain that substance abusers reside to do act according to peers wish.

METHODOLOGY

Preamble

This section describes the research design, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, instrument for data collection, validity and reliability of instrument, ethical consideration, and procedure for data analysis.

Research design

A descriptive cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. It is a non-experimental research design that involves selecting and studying of samples derived from populations of interest to ascertain the relative occurrence, distribution and interrelations of variables of sociological and psychological relevance. The descriptive survey permits a researcher to describe conditions as they exist in their natural setting. It also permits orderly collation of data using a questionnaire. This method was considered suitable for the phenomena under study.

Study settings

The setting for this study was Calabar Municipality and Calabar South Local Government Areas, located at the southern part of the State. Calabar Municipality of Cross River State lies between latitudes $5^{\circ}10'11''$ North and longitude $8^{\circ}20'$ East. It is bounded to the North by Odukpani Local Government Area, to the East by the Great Qua River, and to the West by Calabar River. It has a total land mass of 331.551m^2 . The climate of Ikot Ansa is characterized by high rainfall and high temperature, hence a rain forest vegetation type is found there. It consists of 10 political wards namely, Akim, Big Qua, Diamond, Ediba, EdimEtop, Ikot Ansa, Ikot Effanga, Ikot Ishie, Ikot Omia, and Kasuka. The traditional occupation of the people is farming, trading and fishing. Majority of them are however public servants.

Calabar South Local Government Area was created in 1996 during the tenure of colonial Umar Farouk Ahmed, the military administration of Cross River State. It is located between latitude $458'$ north and longitude 817° East. The city lies on a peninsula between Cross River State and Great Qua River. It stretches up to the Calabar River. The Efut and the Efiks are the dominant ethnic group in Calabar South Local Government Area but other ethnic strangers like the Ibibio's Annangs, Ijaws, Igbos, Yorubas and Hausas exist. The major occupation of its dwellers is fishing, farming, and trading. Among the major historical site is the ancient Henshaw town beach market, the ancient French company building at Marina Road, Ekpe Store, African Magistrate court, old nature court and Duke town church/church of Scotland Mission etc. Traditionally, it has many clans and villages the principal traditional rulers of the Efiks are called "Etinyins" whiel those of the Efuts are called "Muri's". The people are friendly and accommodating, they love extended family setting which cater for the wellbeing of all members of the family. This explains why they have family houses with to the heads called Etubum/Muri. Their annual festival includes Ekpe Festival, boat regatta, Nnabo etc. The local government has its headquarters at Anantigha which is headed by a chairman. It also has involved 12 wards each headed by a counselor. There are numerous tourism

potentials and artifacts located in the local government. There are also about 12 fishing creeks located in the local government.

Target population

The target population of this study consists of youths (18-35 years) residing in Calabar Metropolis who are either employed or unemployed but are not people who are out of the labour force such as students, homemakers and retirees. To the best knowledge of the researcher, there is currently no formal population record for this category of youths in the State. Hence, the target population for this study is unknown.

Sample and sampling technique

The sample size for the quantitative study was determined using formula for estimating a single finite proportion or percentage for a categorical outcome variable. This formula is used because the accessible population for this study is unknown. The formula is as stated below:

$$n = \frac{Z^2Pq}{d^2}$$

Where n = Sample size

Z = Standard normal deviation score at 95% confidence interval (1.96)

P = 87.3% (0.873) being the proportion of the population that have used psychoactive substance (Oshodi et al., 2019)

q = Proportion for non-occurrence (1 - P) = 1 - 0.873 = 0.127

d = Desired level of precision set at 5%

Therefore:

n = ?

Z = 1.96

P = proportion of population = 0.873

q = (1 - P) = 1 - 0.873 = 0.127

d = 0.05

Hence, substituting these parameters in the formula:

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.873 \times 0.127}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.873 \times 0.127}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.1109}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.4259}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 170.36$$

$$n = 170 \text{ approximately}$$

Factoring the non-response rate of 10% (0.10): the sample size will increase by 10%

Applying the formula

$$\frac{N}{1 - \text{Non-response rate}}$$

Where $n =$ Derived sample size $= 170$

Non-response rate of 10% $= 0.10$

Substituting these figures in the formula, gives:

$$n = \frac{170}{0.90}$$

$$n = 188.89 = \text{approximately } 189$$

Hence, a sample of 189 was used for the study.

A multistage sampling procedure was adopted to select participants for this study using clusters as sampling unit except at the last stage of selection. These involved a total of five (5) stages including the selection of Local Governments, wards, streets/villages, households, and the participants respectively. Adopting the cluster sampling was based on the fact that the population of interest (youths 18-35 years) to the researcher exists as a hierarchy of groups or “clusters”. That is to say that Calabar Metropolis is a cluster of Local Government Areas (LGAs); each of these LGAs comprises of Political wards; these wards are made up of streets, the streets are made up of households, and youths of interest to the researcher are found in these households. These individuals (youths 18-35 years) could be seen as a cluster since they are alike with respect to the characteristics relevant to the subject under consideration. Analysis of the selection processes involve in each of the stages is as follows:

Stage 1: Selection of LGAs

Youths (18-35 years) were grouped or clustered based on the LGAs. Calabar Metropolis is made up of two (2) LGAs. Since there are only two LGAs, the researcher purposively studied the two (2) LGAs because they are few. Thus, no selection was applicable at this stage.

Stage 2: Selection of Wards

Four (4) wards were selected respectively from each of the two (2) LGAs using simple random sampling. There is a total of twenty-two (22) political wards in Calabar Metropolis

comprising of 10 wards from Calabar Municipality LGA and 12 wards from Calabar South LGA. Therefore, a total of eight (8) wards were randomly selected from the 22 wards that make up the study area.

Stage 3: Selection of streets

Five (5) streets were selected each from the 8 wards selected in stage 2 above using random sampling method of balloting with replacement. In each of the selected wards, the researcher listed all the streets in that ward and represent each of them with a number. Thereafter, balloting with replacement was applied to pick only three (3) of the streets for the study. With this, a total of forty (40) streets/villages were randomly selected across the 8 political wards selected in the preceding stage.

Stage 4: Selection of households

In each of the five (5) streets selected in stage 3 above, the researcher proportionately allocated the sample size to each of the selected streets. That is, the researcher counted the number of households in the street and use proportionate sampling method to allocate sample size to such a street. Afterward, a systematic random sampling was used to select the households for the study.

Stage 5: Selection of participants

In each of the household selected, one youth (age 18-35 years) who meets the inclusion criteria was selected to participate in the study. And, if there was more than one of such individuals in a selected household, simple random sampling technique of balloting without replacement (exhaustive balloting) was used to select only one youth to participate in the study. However, where there was no youth in a selected household who meets the criteria for inclusion, the household immediately after the selected household was used for the study without disrupting the original arrangement of selection applicable in that street.

Instrument for data collection

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher with the aid of the researcher's supervisor. The questionnaire was divided into four (4) sections; sections A, B, C and D. Section A was designed to collect the respondents' demographic data. While sections B, C and D consist of items which sought information on major variables used in the study that is: the prevalence of psychoactive substance, types of psychoactive substance used, and the reasons for using psychoactive substances. Items under section D were measured using 4 points Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Validity and reliability of instrument

To establish the validity of the instrument, items were drawn to cover the variables under study. In addition, the questionnaire was submitted to and vetted by the researcher's supervisor and other experts. With this, face validity were established.

To ensure that the instrument is reliable, a pilot study was conducted by the researcher using twenty (20) youths in the study area who were not part of the main study. Therefore, twenty (20) copies of the questionnaire were printed and administered to these youths who responded to its items and returned same to the researcher. Their responses were coded and scored, and Pearson Product Moment of Correlation analysis conducted. Reliability coefficient of the range 0.822-0.927 was obtained for the instrument. This shows that the instrument is reliable, hence, could accurately measure the variables under study.

Table 1: Estimation of Reliability Coefficient through test-retest technique

S/No	Variables	N	Test positions	$\bar{X}$	SD	r-cal
1.	Prevalence of psychoactive substance	20	1 st test 2 nd test	3.27 3.43	0.83 0.73	0.877
2.	Types of psychoactive substance use	20	1 st test 2 nd test	7.20 7.10	0.48 0.64	0.927
3.	Reasons for using psychoactive substances	20	1 st test 2 nd test	17.60 16.63	3.67 3.56	0.822

Source: *Questionnaire*

Pilot study

A pilot study was carried out among youths at Odukpani, Cross River State to test the reliability and validity of the data collection instrument. The result from the pre-testing was not included in the study as it was used in better understanding of the research instrument as well as the flow and time used to complete each questionnaire.

Method of data collection

Data was collected through face-to-face administration of questionnaires to the respondents. To facilitate quick and easy administration and collection of the questionnaire, the researcher recruited two (2) research assistants after giving them necessary training on the sampling procedure. The administration took a period of two (2) weeks. Completed questionnaires were retrieved on the spot. A total of 189 questionnaires were administered to the respondents and same were retrieved giving a 100% response rate.

Method of data analysis

Data collected from the respondents were grouped, analyzed, and interpreted using frequency and simple percentages. Association between variables was achieved using Chi-square statistics significant at 0.05.

Ethical consideration

For the success of this research work, some ethical issues were considered. A letter of introduction was obtained from the Head of Department of Nursing Science, National Open, Calabar study Centre. This was to enable the researcher obtain approval from the Cross River State Ministry of Health Ethical Committee. After ethical clearance, permission was sought and obtained from the research and ethical community of the two LGAs used for the study. The principle of voluntary participation through informed consent from the respondents was observed. Also, the principle of non-maleficent was ensued by maintaining respondents' anonymity. All authors of books and other researcher's whose work are used in the study were properly referenced.

RESULTS

Preamble

One hundred and eighty-nine (189) questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, same were properly filled and returned to the researcher giving a 100% response rate. The questionnaires were sorted, and data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics including frequency counts, simple percentages, weighted mean score, and Chi-square test of association significant at 0.05. This chapter is organized under the following sub-headings; presentation and analysis of demographic data; and analysis of research questions.

Presentation and analysis of demographic data

Table2: Distribution of respondents' demographic characteristics (n = 189)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender:		
Male	79	41.8
Female	110	58.2
Total	189	100
Age:		
18 – 27 years	18	9.5
28 – 37 years	90	47.6
Above 37 years	81	42.8
Total	189	100
Religion:		
Islam	-	0.0
Christianity	171	90.5
Traditional	18	9.5
Total	189	100
Place of residence		
Calabar South	105	55.6
Calabar Municipality	84	44.4
Total	189	100

Family Type:

Monogamous	69	36.5
Polygamous	96	50.9
Single Parent	24	12.7
Total	189	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

Table 2 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The Table shows that among the 286 respondents used for the study, most 110 (58.2%) were female; a greater proportion 90 (47.6%) were between 28-37 years of age; nearly all 171 (90.5%) of them were Christians; many 105 (55.6%) resides in Calabar South, while slightly above half 96 (50.9%) were from polygamous families.

Analysis of research questions

Research question 1: What is the prevalence of psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis?

Items of the questionnaire related to the question above were sorted and results presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Prevalence of psychoactive substance use among the respondents (n = 189)

S/No	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Have you used drugs other than those required for medical reasons?		
	Yes	25	13.2
	No	189	100
	Total		
2.	If yes, are you currently using these drugs?		
	Yes	164	86.8
	No	-	0.0
	Total	164	86.8
3.	How often do you use these drugs?		
	Very often		
	Often	42	22.2
	Sometimes	64	33.9
	Rarely	28	14.8
	Total	30	15.9
		164	86.7
4.	At what age did you used drugs for the first time?		

Less than 12 years	22	11.6
12 – 14 years	62	32.8
15 years & above	80	42.3
Total	164	86.7

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

The prevalence of psychoactive substance use is presented in Table 3. According to the Table, majority 164 (86.7%) of the 189 youths used for the study responded ‘yes’ that they’ve used drugs other than those required for medical reasons. All the respondents who have used drugs are currently using it. Among these respondents, many 64 (33.9%) used it often, and almost half 80 (42.3%) of them first began to use these substances when they were 15 years of age and above.

Research question 2: What are the types of psychoactive substances commonly used among youths in Calabar Metropolis?

To answer the above research question, items under section C of the research questionnaire were sorted and presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Types of psychoactive substances commonly used by the respondents (n = 164)

S/No	Types of psychoactive substance used	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Alcohol	160	97.6
2.	Tobacco	46	28.0
3.	Marijuana	9	5.5
4.	Codeine	-	0.0
5.	Cannabis	28	17.1
6.	Combine	117	71.3
7.	Kola-nut	10	6.1
8.	Cocaine	-	0.0
9.	Tramadol	9	5.5

Source: Fieldwork, 2024.

Table 4 presents the types of psychoactive substances commonly used by the respondents. The Table shows that the most commonly used psychoactive substance used by the respondents was alcohol 160 (97.6%), followed by combine (extract from combination of cannabis and alcohol) 117 (71.3%), tobacco 46 (28.0%), cannabis 28 (17.1%), kola-nut 10 (6.1%), tramadol 9 (5.5%), and marijuana 9 (5.5%). Hence, the most commonly used psychoactive substance among the youths was alcohol.

Research question 3: What are the reasons for psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis?

To answer the above research questions, items 11 – 17 of the research questionnaires were sorted and presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Reasons why respondents use psychoactive substances (n = 189)

S/No.	Reasons for using psychoactive substance	Weighted mean	Standard deviation	Decision
12.	For curiosity	2.19	0.66	Insignificant
13.	To improve general condition	2.08	0.21	Insignificant
14.	To boost memory before examination	1.83	0.14	Insignificant
15.	To achieve feelings of happiness and joy	2.07	0.19	Insignificant
16.	For conformity with peers	3.51	0.36	Significant
17.	To boost confidence	3.74	0.32	Significant
18.	For experimentation	3.12	0.17	Significant

Decision Rule: $\bar{x} > 2.50 = \text{Significant}$ $\bar{x} \leq 2.50 = \text{Insignificant}$

Table 5 presents the reasons why the youths use psychoactive substances. Data obtained under this research question was summarized using the weighted mean score. Based on the decision rule stated below the Table, the significant reasons why the youths used psychoactive substances include to conform to peers (3.51±0.36), boost confidence (3.74±0.32), and for experimentation (3.12±0.17). Thus, youths used psychoactive substances mostly to boost their confidence, conform to their peers, and for experimentation purpose.

Research question 4: What are the demographic determinants of psychoactive substances use among youths in Calabar Metropolis?

To answer this question, chi-square test of association was conducted to associate the respondents' demographic characteristics with use of psychoactive substances. This test was conducted at $p < 0.05$. The results of this test are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Contingency Chi-square analysis showing the association between the students' demographic characteristics and use of psychoactive substance (n = 189)

Students' demographic characteristics	Use of Psychoactive substance			X ²	P-value	Decision
	Used	Did not use	Row Total			
Gender:						
Male	72	7	79	21.237	<0.05	Significant
Female	92	18	110			
Column Total	164	25	189			
Age						
18 – 27 years	7	11	18	9.783	<0.05	Significant
28 – 37 years	83	7	90			
Above 37 years	74	7	81			
Column Total	164	25	189			
Place of residence						
Calabar South	94	11	105	4.291	<0.05	Significant
Calabar	70	14	84			

Municipality	164	25	189			
Column Total						
Religion						
Muslim	0	0	0			
Christianity	151	20	171	1.559	>0.05	Not significant
Traditional	13	5	18			
Column Total	164	25	189			
Family Type						
Monogamous	51	18	69			
Polygamous	93	3	96	10.558	<0.05	Significant
Single parent	20	4	24			
Column Total	164	25	189			

Significant at 0.05

Table 6 above presents the result of the Chi-square test of association conducted to ascertain the association between youths' demographics and use of psychoactive substance among the study participants. Based on the decision rule for this analysis, the demographic characteristics of youths that significantly associated with use of psychoactive substances was the youths' sex, age, place of residence, and family type ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the demographic determinants of psychoactive substance use include sex, age, place of residence, and family type.

Discussion of findings

Findings of this study are discussed below in line with the research objectives.

Prevalence of psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar Metropolis

Findings of this study shows that a great majority of the youths have used and are currently using psychoactive substance. Most of them often used these substances, and a greater percentage of these youths began using drugs for the first time when they were 15 years and above. This finding is in line with finding obtained by Oshodi et al (2019) in a related study conducted to examine the prevalence and associated factors of substance use among secondary school students in an urban setting in Nigeria. These authors reported an overall lifetime prevalence of substance among students used for their study to be as high as 87.3% with a current use prevalence of 69.2%. Similarly, Vincent et al (2021) obtained similar finding in another related conducted to assess the prevalence and pattern of psychoactive substance use among secondary school students in a community secondary school in Umuna. The authors reported that more than half of the students use substance mainly on daily basis which agrees with findings of the present study where more than half of the study participants were using psychoactive substance, and most of them used it frequently.

Types of psychoactive substances commonly used by youths in Calabar Metropolis

Results of the study revealed that the most commonly used psychoactive substances used by the respondents was alcohol, followed by combine (extract from combination of cannabis alcohol), tobacco, cannabis, kola-nut, tramadol, and marijuana. Hence, the mostly used psychoactive substance was alcohol. These findings confirm the findings of Onukogu et al (2019) who reported that alcohol was the most frequent psychoactive substances used by secondary school students in Calabar. However, among secondary school students in five public schools in Surulere, Lagos, Oshodi et al (2019) found that caffeine (kolanut and coffee) was the most common substance used by these students. This contradict finding of the present study as the mostly used psychoactive substances were analgesic and alcohol. This difference in findings could be due to the settings and target population of both study which are culturally sensitive; hence, substance use is likely to be influenced by culture and tradition applicable to these settings.

Reasons for using psychoactive substances among youths in Calabar Metropolis

Findings of the present study revealed that the significant reasons why youths used psychoactive substances include conforming to peers, boost confidence, and for experimentation purpose. Thus, youths use psychoactive substances mostly to boost their confidence, conform to their peers, and for experimentation purpose. These findings are supported by findings obtained by Johnson et al (2018) who reported that the influence of peer group, stress and curiosity, being the most common factors responsible to predispose students to psychoactive substance use. On the other hand, Amdzaranda et al (2019) reported in a related study conducted by inmates in Nigeria that stimulants consumption was associated with unemployment, several arrest for drug related offense, many imprisonments and longer term/duration of imprisonment. The observed difference in findings between the studies is due to the study population.

Demographic determinants of psychoactive substance use among youths in Calabar

Metropolis

Results of the Chi-square test of association conducted to ascertain the association between the youths' demographics and use of psychoactive substance among the study participants revealed that the demographic characteristics of the youths that significantly associated with use of psychoactive substances were sex, age, place of residence, and family type ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the demographic determinants of psychoactive substance use include sex, age, place of residence, and family type. This agrees with Mbachu et al (2020) who found that the prevalence of psychoactive substance used was significantly associated with sex, age, and low socio-economic status. On the same note, Johnson et al (2018) in a related study reported that a statistically significant association existed between substance use and age, and sex, and family type. This agrees with findings of the present study.

Implication of the study to nursing

The study revealed that the use of psychoactive substance is very prevalent among youths is strongly associated their sex, age, place of residence, and family type; and most of these youths take drugs to conform with their peer. This indicates the need for the nurses to organize community-based health education intervention specially designed to discourage the use of illicit drugs by pointing out the dangers associated with the use of psychoactive substances. This programme should be implemented mostly in schools where the use of these substances begins.

Limitations of the study

Major problems that were encountered in this study were the inability to access enough written materials related to the topic of this research. Also, the researcher encountered difficulties in distributing the questionnaires used for the study. Information was not readily given by the respondents, but with determination, perseverance and a high sense of commitment, the researcher overcame these obstacles. This brought about the successful completion of this study.

Summary of the study

The main aim of the study was to assess the prevalence of psychoactive substances use among youths in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to; determine the prevalence of psychoactive substance use among youths; identify the types of psychoactive substances commonly used by youths; examine the reasons for psychoactive substance use among the youths; and ascertain the demographic determinants of psychoactive substance use among the youths. To achieve the set goals, four (4) research questions were raised as guide to the study. In addition, literature related to the topic was reviewed conceptually and empirically to further give insight on the topic to the researcher. The social cognitive theory was found applicable to the study; hence, was adopted as a theoretical guide. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was the research design used to study a total of 189 youths selected from the study area using the multi-stage technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire constructed by the researcher and submitted to the researcher's supervisor who vetted the items, made relevant changes, and certified that the instrument could adequately measure what it is purported to measure. With this, face and content validity were established. Twenty (20) copies of the validated questionnaire were pretested among youths in the study area who were not included in the main study. Using test-retest reliability test, scores in the respective tests were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, and a reliability of the range 0.822-0.927 was obtained indicating that the instrument is reliable and should be used for data collection. A total of 189 copies of the validated and reliable questionnaire were administered to the respondents after receiving ethical approval to conduct the study. Same were properly filled and returned to the researcher at the spot giving a 100% response rate. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency count, simple percentage, and weighted mean scores, while the association between variables was achieved using Chi-square test of association with its

significant level set at 0.05. Findings of the study revealed that majority 164 (86.7%) of the youths have used drugs other than those required for medical reasons. The most commonly used psychoactive substance used by the respondents was alcohol 160 (97.6%), followed by combine (extract from combination of cannabis alcohol), tobacco 46 (28.0%), cannabis 28 (17.1%), kola-nut 10 (6.1%), tramadol 9 (5.5%), and marijuana 9 (5.5%). The significant reasons why the students used psychoactive substances include to conform to peers (3.51 ± 0.36), boost confidence (3.74 ± 0.32), and for experimentation (3.12 ± 0.17). Lastly, the demographic characteristics of the students that significantly associated with use of psychoactive substances was sex, age, place of residence, and family type ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

In consonance with findings of this study, it is concluded that psychoactive substance use is very prevalent among youths in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State. The mostly used substance among these students is alcohol, which is frequently used by the students. The significant reasons for using these substances include conforming to peers, boost confidence, and for experimentation purpose. Finally, use of psychoactive substances was significantly associated with age, sex, place of residence, and family type.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the researcher proffers the following recommendations:

1. Existing policies on restriction of illicit drug use should be strengthened to tame the sources of these drugs and reduce its availability.
2. An enlightenment programme should be designed and implemented in communities especially in Calabar Metropolis to create awareness on the health and legal implications of using psychoactive substances.
3. Community-based policies restricting the use of drugs should be framed and implemented and culprits punished accordingly to serve as a deterrent to other youths who may have wish to indulge in these practices.

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